

Cost-effectiveness analysis of urban nature-based solutions: A stepwise ranking approach

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ABSTRACT

Despite increasing interest in Nature-based Solutions (NbS), there is still a lack of comprehensive understanding regarding the costs of different types of NbS and their variations. Cost information is crucial for economic assessments of the viability of NbS compared to other alternatives. In this paper, we provide an overview of NbS costs in urban settings, drawing primarily from a literature review of both gray and scientific literature. We present cost estimates for establishing green and blue spaces in urban and peri-urban areas, street trees, green roofs, and green walls. Our findings show that median costs are 56 EUR/m² for green spaces, 73 EUR/m³ for blue spaces, and 201 EUR/m² for green roofs.

Furthermore, we demonstrate how an economic assessment can be carried out utilizing the calculated cost estimates while providing a systematic procedure to handle the multiple potential benefits provided by NbS. We argue that a step-wise ranked cost-effectiveness analysis, based on ranking local policy objectives, is a feasible approach for making informed choices on competing solutions relative to conventional cost-effectiveness analysis and cost-benefit analysis. The proposed approach could prove useful due to its relatively straightforward application and the fact that it does not require the aggregation of multiple benefits into one common measurement or valuation unit.

1. Introduction

Cities significantly impact natural energy exchanges and hydrological processes due to the built environment and impermeable surfaces on streets, pavements, and squares. This leads to urban heat islands and increased surface run-off of rainwater, making urban areas particularly susceptible to climate change impacts. These consequences affect human health and wellbeing, cause economic losses, and contribute to social insecurity [1-3]. Additionally, the densely built environment, urban sprawl, and inadequate management of green infrastructure result in declining biodiversity levels and ecological deserts [4,5].

Urban areas and activities are also major sources of soil, air, and water pollution. Soil pollution often stems from industrial activities, waste disposal, and agrochemical use in urban gardens, contaminating soil and groundwater resources [6]. Air pollution, primarily due to transport emissions and industrial activities, has severe repercussions on human health and the environment, including respiratory diseases and climate change [7]. Lastly, water pollution arises from urban wastewater discharge and stormwater runoff, causing eutrophication, loss of

aquatic biodiversity, and negative impacts on drinking water quality and aquatic ecosystems [8].

Nature-based Solutions (NbS) operationalize and encompass a number of terms that work with nature and use nature to help address the above-mentioned challenges, including, for instance, natural water retention measures, blue-green infrastructure and ecosystem-based Disaster Risk Reduction [9]. NbS, by protecting existing habitats, restoring degraded ecosystems, and introducing new habitats in urban dense areas, can contribute to increasing overall resilience, decreasing urban heat stress, reducing flood risks, improving air quality, improving biodiversity, and enhancing water supply and purification [10]. This ultimately leads to improved health and well-being, reducing the pressure and costs on the healthcare system and reducing damage costs on infrastructure and buildings. Through investment in nature, additional high-skilled and low-skilled jobs are created, with particular potential for helping to include people at the edge of the labor market [11].

The potential of NbS to deliver multiple benefits to society has led to their integration into recent EU policies and strategies as an efficient approach for simultaneously addressing social, economic, and

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environmental challenges. Key policies and strategies incorporating nature-based solutions include the Green Deal [12], the Adaptation Strategy [13], the Urban Agenda [14], the Flood Directive [15], and the Nature Restoration Regulation [16]. By incorporating NbS in these strategic frameworks, the European Union acknowledges the value of NbS in creating resilient and sustainable urban environments while fostering economic growth and social well-being.

The effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of NbS are central to the argument for systematically implementing them across various landscapes, including urban, rural, and coastal areas. Cost-effectiveness is, for instance, embedded in the European Commission's official definition of NbS: "Solutions that are inspired and supported by nature, which are cost-effective, simultaneously provide environmental, social, and economic benefits, and help build resilience. Such solutions integrate more, and more diverse, nature and natural features and processes into cities, landscapes, and seascapes through locally adapted, resource-efficient, and systemic interventions" [17]. Yet, conducting a comprehensive cost-effectiveness assessment of NbS remains inherently difficult due to the absence of consistent and reliable cost data. This paper aims to address this critical gap in the literature by providing more accurate and robust cost estimates for NbS. In doing so, we seek to establish a clearer understanding of the current state of knowledge regarding the costs of NbS, laying the groundwork for future research to further close these gaps and improve the effectiveness of decision-making in this area.

Additionally, defining NbS as cost-effective - as in the definition of the European Commissions - poses a paradox: cost-effectiveness analysis traditionally focuses on a singular outcome, while NbS are designed to deliver multiple benefits. Attempting to capture these multifaceted benefits through a conventional cost-effectiveness lens risks underestimating their overall value.

To address this issue, we propose an expanded cost-effectiveness framework that accounts for the multi-benefit characteristics of NbS. This is done through a stepwise ranking approach, which evaluates and prioritizes local policy objectives while systematically considering the multiple effects of NbS. Crucially, this approach also tackles the practical problem of limited information, particularly regarding the magnitude and scope of the benefits that NbS provide. By simplifying the decision-making process and focusing on readily available data, our method offers a practical yet effective solution for assessing NbS in real-world contexts.

This study derives cost measures through a literature review of the construction and maintenance costs of nature and designed nature areas in urban and peri-urban regions. We report cost measures for various urban green and blue spaces, green roofs, green walls, and street trees. The selected typology reflects the most common and impactful forms of NbS implemented in urban and peri-urban settings [18]. By focusing on these four types, the study captures a broad spectrum of NbS, each of which provides unique ecosystem services while being representative of the diverse strategies that cities employ to integrate nature into built environments.

The cost information was extracted from both scientific literature and gray literature published by consultancy firms and public authorities. Despite the abundance of literature on quantifying the benefits of ecosystem services, both in monetary and non-monetary terms [19–21], the literature on the costs of nature areas in urban settings is not well-developed. We found only a few studies that explicitly focused on costs, with notable exceptions being the work by Blackhurst et al. [22], Jiang et al. [23], and Qiu et al. [24].

In the present paper, cost measures were mainly extracted from the literature, where cost calculations were often secondary to the main objective of the publication. As a result, a structured literature review was deemed impractical. Instead, we conducted a snowball literature review of the construction and maintenance costs of nature areas in urban settings. By following the trail of references from key publications, we were able to gather relevant cost information. Additionally, Aarhus Municipality and Institut Paris Région provided cost measures

based on previous projects conducted within their jurisdictions.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents a generalized cost function for NbS that provides the framework to compare and interpret cost estimates in the following sections. Sections 3 and 4 present cost estimates for green and blue spaces, respectively, while Section 5 presents cost estimates for green roofs. Section 6 focuses on the cost of street trees. In Section 7, we compare the cost measures of the different NbS. We then discuss how the limited cost information can be used to make economic assessments using cost-effectiveness analysis of NbS. To this end, we advocate for a step-wise ranking of policy objectives within a cost-effectiveness analysis, highlighting the novelty of the present paper. Finally, in the concluding section, we summarize the findings of the paper, discuss the application of cost estimates in economic assessments, and outline future research perspectives.

2. A generalized cost function for Nature-based Solutions

In any cost-effectiveness analysis, it is essential to translate diverse cost components into a single, comparable figure. This simplification allows for meaningful comparison between different solutions. Given the complexity of NbS, where both initial construction costs and ongoing maintenance costs vary, we propose an equation that consolidates these costs into a single present value adapted from the classical economic literature [22].

The cost of a NbS is a function of the fixed one-time cost of construction (d) and the ongoing yearly maintenance cost (m). Since people and companies tend to have a preference for present consumption over future consumption, the cost needs to be discounted using a discount rate (r) that weighs future costs over time (t) relative to present costs.

The debate over the discount rate is controversial. In the classical economic literature, the discount rate is often implemented in a way that makes benefits and costs in the future negligible. However, this approach has been criticized in the debate on sustainable development for emphasizing near future issues over long-term issues [25]. To address this concern, some scholars have proposed using a convex discount rate, where the rate decreases over time [26]. However, for simplicity, this paper will apply the classical discount rate.

The present cost (C) of a NbS can be calculated using Eq. (1). The equation can be expanded to contain lifetime consideration - as some constructions will have to be rebuilt while other constructions do not have such temporal constraints.

$$C = o + d + \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{m}{(1+r)^t} \quad (1)$$

Land opportunity cost (o) is added to the equation alongside establishment cost and discounted maintenance cost. In urban areas, competition for space is intense, and land used for NbS could alternatively serve other purposes such as housing or commercial development. The opportunity cost of land, which is the economic potential foregone by choosing NbS over these alternatives, may play a critical role in determining whether a NbS is cost-effective. While recognizing the importance of land opportunity cost, this paper does not delve into its detailed treatment.

The construction and maintenance costs of NbS will vary depending on the maturity of Nature-based Enterprises (NBEs) that supply the NbS. In young NBEs, the solutions tend to be more expensive, but as the industry matures, costs become a competitive advantage and costs tend to decrease [27]. However, since NbS are restricted to geographical space, the industrial life cycle may vary across countries and regions. Some countries may have well-developed industries that provide, for example, green roofs, while others with limited expertise may have few actors and higher prices. Another factor that can contribute to cost differences between countries and regions is material and labor costs, with the latter being particularly important [28]. This means that the cost of labor-intensive projects will likely vary more between countries than the

cost of labor-moderate projects.

3. The cost of green spaces

The term "urban green space" encompasses a diverse range of spaces in urban areas, each serving different purposes. Such spaces can include urban parks, peri-urban nature located in the outskirts of the city, cemeteries, schoolyards, sports grounds, local housing association playgrounds, or scrape land buffering dis-amenities or unused building lots [18,29]. These green spaces have different facilities and will require different investment and maintenance costs.

The cost of establishing an urban green space can involve several elements such as treating contaminated soils, soil preparation, landscape development, planting, and creating additional facilities like benches, gravel roads, playgrounds, and sports facilities. The size of the green space can range from small to several hectares, and the economy of scale can impact the cost. Additionally, the ambition level regarding facilities can affect the cost. Furthermore, labor-intensive activities can influence the establishment cost. Thus, regions with lower labor costs may have a comparative advantage over those with higher labor costs in terms of the cost of establishing a green space.

Table 1 presents cost estimates derived from an extensive literature review that incorporated both scientific and gray literature. To gather relevant studies, we employed a search strategy using Google Scholar, combining search terms "cost," "cost-benefit," and "economic assessment" with specific terms related to NbS, such as "green space," "parks," and "nature." Additionally, we applied a snowball reference approach, tracing citations from key publications to identify further relevant studies, while taking care to avoid circular citations, which were particularly prevalent in much of the literature.

To supplement the initial search and ensure comprehensive coverage, we also utilized the literature search engine Elicit.org, which helped us verify that no significant studies were overlooked. This dual approach of combining both general and targeted search techniques allowed us to compile the cost estimates presented in Table 1.

To ensure consistency and comparability across various data sources and years, all cost figures are reported in EUR 2021 prices. This adjustment involved two key steps using the R library priceR [49]. First, costs from different years were converted into their 2021 local currency equivalents using the *adjust_for_inflation* function. This function employs historical inflation rates from the World Bank API to accurately reflect changes in cost levels over time, as proscribed in 'Principles of Macroeconomics [50]. Following this, the *convert_currencies* function was used to convert these adjusted figures from local currencies into EUR, applying the average exchange rates for 2021. This two-step process ensures that the costs presented are not only updated to reflect current values accurately but are also standardized in a single currency. This standardization allows for straightforward comparisons across the various studies and countries included in our analysis.

The cost measures in Table 1 are based on multiple and single projects, as well as general assessments. As the cost figures were not the main focus of the reviewed publications, the documentation of these cost figures in the referenced literature is limited. Therefore, the presented cost figures should be interpreted cautiously, not as exact values but as an impression of the likely cost level of green spaces.

Table 1 provides cost estimates for various types of green spaces across Europe, the US, and China, including wadis, swales, water retention areas, urban parks, urban forestry, and peri-urban nature. The establishment cost of green space has a mean of 59.98 EUR/m² and a median of 31.73 EUR/m². The cost distribution is right-skewed, with a maximum establishment price of 323 EUR/m² and a minimum of 1.7 EUR/m². However, these cost figures should be interpreted with care, as they are not well-documented in the referenced literature and may include activities not included in other cost measures. Generally, the establishment cost is higher for European and US sources and cheaper for Chinese sources. Schoolyards and intensively managed park areas,

Table 1
Cost of green spaces (in 2021 prices).

Source	Description	Country	Year	Establishment costs EUR/m ²	Maintenance costs EUR/m ²
[30]	Swales	Denmark	2017	69.26	3.47
[30]	Swales-trench	Denmark	2017	76.25	4.16
[30]	Swales	Denmark	2017	48.55	2.42
[31]	Swales	Denmark	2021	134.48	
[32]	Swales	UK	2015	13.13	
[32]	Swales	UK	2015	19.71	0.13
[32]	Swales	UK	2015	23.64	0.13
[32]	Swales	UK	2015	26.27	0.13
[33]	Swales	US	2018	37.32	0.05
[33]	Swales	US	2018	122.21	1.78
[34]	Swales	UK	2007	20.55	0.24
[35]	Swales	EU	2018	244	0.52
[36]	Swales	EU	2018	70	
[24]	Infiltration trench	China	2019	29.84	
[36]	Infiltration trench	EU	2018	57	
[24]	Bioretention cell	China	2019	103.04	
[24]	Vegetated filter strip	China	2019	56.01	
[36]	Raingarden	EU	2018	19	
[36]	Raingarden	EU	2018	55	
[37]	Green space to flood reduction	China	2019	2.16	
[37]	Green space to flood reduction	China		6.61	
[38]	Green space to flood reduction	China	2015	5.87	0.18
[39]	Wet-green park	Italy	2015	88.13	0.98
[40]	Park lawn	China	2012		0.24
[40]	Lawn	China	2012		0.93
[40]	Lawn	China	2012		0.62
[35]	Lawn	EU	2018	2.36	0.38
[35]	Park forest	EU	2018	6.76	1.67
[35]	Park	EU	2018		3.12
[35]	Park	EU	2018		12.48
[41]	Brownfield to park	Canada	2003	36.49	
[42]	Wasteland to park	France	2021	6.8	
[43]	Green space	Spain	2019	23.29	
[44]	Park	US	2007	183.79	
[31]	Intensive city park	Denmark	2021	80.68	4.03
[31]	Peri-urban green space	Denmark	2021	201.72	4.03
[45]	Park maintenance	Italy	2012		1.19
[45]	Park maintenance	Italy	2012		0.42
[45]	Park maintenance	Italy	2012		2.96
[42]	Peri-urban nature	France	2021	13.9	
[46]	Park extensive	China	2008	1.73	
[46]	Park extensive	China	2008	25.9	
[31]	Extensive park	Denmark	2021	33.62	1.61
[42]	Peri-urban nature	France	2021	7.5	
[47]	Urban forestry	US	2006	322.76	
[48]	Urban forestry	Chile	2008		0.06
[31]	Peri-urban forest	Denmark	2021	4.03	0.4

which are commonly found in inner-city areas, have the highest establishment cost, while smaller green spaces are less expensive. Peri-urban nature, located at the fringes of a city, such as urban forests and extensively managed green spaces, is the cheapest type of green space.

The mean maintenance cost of urban green spaces is 1.79 EUR/m², while the median maintenance cost stands at 0.93 EUR/m². The maximum maintenance cost reaches 12.48 EUR/m², and the minimum cost is 0.05 EUR/m². Once again, we observe the lowest cost in China and higher maintenance costs in European countries and the US. The higher maintenance costs are likely associated with green spaces that require intensive management, whereas lower maintenance costs can be attributed to regions with either low labor costs or low labor intensity.

4. The cost of blue spaces

Blue spaces in urban areas can include lakes, ponds, streams, and rivers, while in the outskirts of a city, they may also refer to wetlands. The construction and maintenance of blue spaces often entail the removal of existing land use, excavation, soil removal, the addition of coarse material, creation of impermeable layers, establishment of potential pumping stations, landscape development, planting, and sowing vegetation along the blue space banks [51]. Moreover, the installation of facilities, such as benches, bridges, and floating pontoons, can enhance the recreational experience of the blue space.

The cost of construction is also a function of the size of the blue space. In absolute terms, costs will increase with the size of the blue space; however, due to economies of scale, the relative cost is likely to decrease. Investment and maintenance costs are influenced by labor costs and labor intensity of the projects. Depending on the specific context, constructing a blue space can be as affordable as simply stopping groundwater pumping. Conversely, in densely urbanized areas, costs associated with land-use removal, such as de-paving, will drive the expenses higher.

The construction and maintenance costs of blue spaces are presented in Table 2. The literature used to compile these estimates was gathered in a manner similar to that for green spaces, with search terms adjusted to focus on NbS such as “lake”, “pond”, “river”, “stream”, and “wetland”. All cost figures in the table are expressed in 2021 Euro prices, following the same methodology outlined in Section 3 for green spaces. The costs have been adjusted for inflation to 2021 values in their local currencies and then converted into EUR. The figures in Table 2 are based on multiple projects, single projects, and general assessments. While these cost figures should not be considered exact numbers, they do provide an impression of the likely cost levels for urban blue spaces. Moreover, the information in the table offers valuable insights into the cost levels for different types of blue spaces and the extent to which costs vary worldwide.

Table 2 features cost estimates primarily covering blue spaces from Europe, the US, and China, including smaller blue spaces such as lakes, ponds, streams, rivers, and wetlands. The mean establishment cost for a pond or a lake is 104.36 EUR/m³, with a median cost of 69.17 EUR/m³. Establishment costs for lakes and ponds are particularly high in the Danish sources, while they are extremely low in the Brazilian case study references. The Chinese cost figures in Table 2 are all above the mean values. This cost discrepancy is likely a result of context-specific factors related to the level of urban development of the reported projects. On average, maintaining lakes or ponds costs 2586.49 EUR/basin, with a median maintenance cost of 1386 EUR/basin.

Table 2 also reports the costs of streams and rivers, with the Paris Region having experience with several river-reopening and river-restoration projects. In these examples, previously piped or straightened streams and rivers are reestablished as “natural” hydrological systems. The cost of reopening a river or stream ranges from 5.8 EUR/m to 13,650 EUR/m. This substantial difference can be attributed to the specific urban context of the reported projects, which vary from predominantly rural to highly developed urban areas. The reported Danish

Table 2
Cost of blue spaces (in 2021 prices).

Source	Description	Country	Year	Establishment costs EUR/unit	Maintenance costs EUR/unit
[30]	Lake	Denmark	2017	277.36 /m ³	554.73 /basin
[30]	Lake	Denmark	2017	69.34 /m ³	277 /basin
[30]	Lake	Denmark	2017	554.73 /m ³	1386 /basin
[32]	Pond	UK	2015	19.71 /m ³	1320 /basin
[32]	Pond	UK	2015	32.84 /m ³	3960 /basin
[32]	Pond	UK	2015	21.02 /m ³	2640 /basin
[52]	Pond	USA	1999	19.6 /m ³	
[53]	Pond	USA	1996	11.11 /m ³	1821.6 /basin
[53]	Pond	USA	1996	24.98 /m ³	12,033 /basin
[54]	Pond	Hongkong	2016	132.09 /m ³	469,67 /basin
[54]	Pond	Hongkong	2016	138.62 /m ³	469.367 /basin
[38]	Pond	China	2015	117.35 /m ³	3520 /basin
[55]	Pond	Brazil	2017	4.37 /m ³	
[31]	Pond	Denmark	2021	80.69 /m ³	
[35]	Pond	EU	2018	97 /m ³	
[56]	Pond	US	1997	69 /m ³	
[30]	Stream (1m*1m)	Denmark	2017	104 /m	3 /m
[42]	Stream (0.5m*1m)	Denmark	2017	90 /m	2 /m
[42]	Stream (0.5m*2m)	Denmark	2017	117 /m	3.6 /m
[42]	Stream (1m*2m)	Denmark	2017	124 /m	5 /m
[42]	River Reopening	France	2014	5.8 /m	
[42]	River Reopening	France	2012	13,650 /m	
[42]	River Reopening	France	2014	126 /m	
[42]	River Reopening	France	2014	578 /m	
[42]	River Reopening	France	2014	1051 /m	
[42]	Riverbank restoration	France	2018	2667 /m	
[42]	Riverbank restoration	France	2020	695 /m	
[57]	Wetland	US	2016	0.94 /m ²	0.07 /m ²
[58]	Wetland	US	2016	4.28 /m ²	
[59]	Wetland	US	2018	0.04 /m ²	0.5 /m ²
[42]	Wetland restoration	France	2018	0.5 /m ²	
[42]	Wetland restoration	France	2018	2.4 /m ²	0.01 m ²

cost figures for small streams reopening represent lower cost estimates (90–124 EUR/m) compared to the cost estimate from the Paris region. Maintenance costs are reported to range between 2–5 EUR/m.

Table 2 also includes cost information on wetland construction from the US and France. The costs range from 0.04 EUR/m² to 4.28 EUR/m², with a mean cost of 1.63 EUR/m² and a median cost of 0.9 EUR/m². Although the units differ between wetlands and other blue spaces, it is evident that the cost of wetlands is much lower than that of other types of blue spaces, such as ponds, lakes, and streams. However, the cost figures in Table 2 do not account for land opportunity costs. As a result, despite the lower costs of wetlands, they may still be the most expensive blue spaces in developed urban areas, while potentially being more competitive in the fringes of large cities.

5. The cost of green roofs

Green roofs can be categorized as either extensive or intensive. The distinction between these two types of green roofs lies in the thickness of the growth media. On average, extensive green roofs have a 20 cm

growth media, while intensive green roofs have a growth media of around 50 cm [60]. This difference in construction implies that extensive green roofs can, in most cases, be retrofitted to regular houses without the need to strengthen the load-bearing elements of the building. Conversely, intensive green roofs can only be retrofitted to buildings that have been designed to withstand heavy loads or specifically constructed for an intensive green roof. Another distinction between extensive and intensive green roofs is that the latter can only support resilient drought-resistant plant growth, such as sedum plants, while the former can sustain a variety of plants similar to those growing on the land surface.

Table 3 provides the construction and maintenance costs of green roofs. The literature for these estimates was gathered using a similar search strategy as with green and blue spaces, but with search terms tailored to focus on "green roofs," "extensive green roofs," and "intensive green roofs." As with the previous tables, all cost figures are converted to 2021 Euro prices, ensuring consistency in the cost measures across

Table 3
Cost of green roofs (in 2021 prices).

Source	Description	Country	Year	Establishment costs EUR/m ²	Maintenance costs EUR/m ²
[61]	Extensive	US	2011	19.57	0.25
[54]	Extensive	US-Seattle	2016	235.5	54.59
[33]	Extensive	US	2018	112.03	0.94
[62]	Extensive	US	2016	195.44	
[60]	Extensive	Canada	2012	119.9	0.66
[60]	Extensive	Canada	2012	152.5	12.84
[32]	Extensive	UK	2015	117.82	
[32]	Extensive	UK	2015	105.11	
[42]	Extensive	France	2015	63	11.77
[63]	Extensive	Netherlands	2008	127.94	1.16
[64]	Extensive	Austria	2018	59.66	0.66
[31]	Extensive	Denmark	2021	107.58	1.34
[54]	Extensive	Hongkong	2016	145	14.56
[65]	Extensive	South Korea	2019	96.84	1.27
[66]	Extensive	Singapore	2003		3.91
[64]	Extensive	Hongkong	2018	92.55	4.11
[24]	Extensive	China	2019	6.27	
[67]	Extensive	Malaysia	2016	65.23	0.22
[67]	Extensive	Malaysia	2016	86.43	0.7
[67]	Extensive	Malaysia	2016	208.74	5.67
[68]	Extensive	South Africa	2013	38.39	
[69]	Extensive	several	2019	91.59	4.14
[35]	Extensive	EU	2018	93.6	
[35]	Extensive	EU	2018	156	3.12
[36]	Extensive	EU	2018	120	
[36]	Extensive	EU	2018	149	
[35]	Intensive	EU	2018		12.48
[60]	Intensive	Canada	2012	499.02	12.85
[61]	Intensive	US	2011	26.09	0.25
[70]	Intensive	US	2005	176.94	
[33]	Intensive	US	2018	503.72	27.04
[62]	Intensive	US	2016	293.56	7.28
[42]	Intensive	France	2015	185	14.01
[42]	Semi-Intensive	France	2015	108	12.64
[31]	Intensive	Denmark	2021	268.96	4.03
[66]	Intensive	Singapore	2003	192.43	4.24
[69]	Intensive	several	2019	334.45	7.5
[31]	Green wall (climbing)	Denmark	2021	1.35	1.08
[42]	Green wall (tablecloth)	France	2015	797	61
[42]	Green wall (performed)	France	2015	474	42
[42]	Green wall (gabion)	France	2015	606	44
[42]	Green wall (hanging)	France	2015	572	42
[42]	Green wall (climbing)	France	2015	55	9.5

different types of NbS. The methodology used for inflation adjustment and currency conversion is identical to that outlined in Section 3, allowing for a uniform comparison of costs between green roofs and other solutions.

Green roofs are more similar to one another than, for instance, green and blue spaces. However, differences still exist depending on building codes, knowledge base, and competition among roof providers. A green roof typically consists of a plant layer, a growing media, a filter layer, a root barrier layer, and a protection layer [62]. The cost of construction will vary according to the materials used, the skillset of the installers, and the general labor costs in the area. We find that the average cost of establishing an extensive green roof is 110.62 EUR/m², with a median cost of 107.58 EUR/m² (see Table 3). The average maintenance cost is 6.77 EUR/m², with a median of 2.33 EUR/m². The establishment cost of green roofs does not exhibit substantial variability when compared to the green and blue space cost figures reported earlier.

The average construction cost for an intensive roof is 275.57 EUR/m², with a median cost of 268.96 EUR/m². The construction cost figures display a left-leaning distribution, with a few relatively inexpensive cost figures and several cost measures above 300 EUR/m². The average maintenance cost is 9.96 EUR/m², and the median cost is 7.5 EUR/m². According to Table 3, the construction cost of an intensive roof appears to be between double and triple that of an extensive roof, a relationship that has been previously found in the literature (e.g., [60]). Aarhus Municipality and Paris Region have also provided cost estimates for vertical greening of buildings in the form of green walls. It appears that climbing plants are the most cost-effective green wall solution, while other types of green walls, where plants grow above the ground, are considerably more expensive.

6. The cost of street trees

The investment and maintenance costs of trees placed along urban streets are presented in Table 4. The literature used to compile these estimates was collected similarly to that of green spaces, with search terms adjusted to include "street trees," "urban trees," and "urban forestry." As with the other tables, all cost figures are expressed in 2021 Euro prices, ensuring consistency across the various NbS. The inflation adjustment and currency conversion methodology, as described in Section 3, was applied here as well, allowing for direct comparisons between the costs of street trees and other NbS like green spaces and green roofs.

The average investment cost for street trees is 1352.99 EUR/tree, and the median investment cost is 203 EUR/tree. The investment cost figures exhibit a heavy-tailed, right-leaning distribution, primarily due to cost estimates provided by Aarhus Municipality. Therefore, the most relevant investment cost number is the median cost of 203 EUR/tree. The difference in cost between Aarhus Municipality and the other sources is partly attributable to the de-pavement cost that Aarhus Municipality includes in their cost figures. The mean maintenance cost is 32.94 EUR/tree, and the median cost is 26.62 EUR/tree. A few references have presented the cost in square meters that have not been translated into a tree unit. We leave it to the reader to translate the number of trees to square meters - or the other way around - thus refraining from making additional assumptions.

7. Summing up the cost estimates

The cost estimates presented in Tables 1-4 provide an overview of the construction and maintenance costs of various urban and peri-urban NbS. The cost figures presented in the tables exhibit a large variability, reflecting the different definitions of cost estimates. These are largely dependent on the cost elements that are included or excluded from the cost figures reported by different sources. It has not been possible to access primary cost data. Thus, the reported cost estimates are secondary sources and must be interpreted with caution.

Table 4
Cost of street trees (in 2021 prices).

Source	Description	Country	Year	Unit	Establishment costs EUR/unit	Maintenance costs EUR/unit
[33]	Street trees	US-New York	2018	m ²	9.87	7.74
[33]	green space	US-New York	2018	m ²	236.84	
[71]	Street trees	US - Fort Collins	2005	tree	258.06	33.26
[71]	Street trees	US - Cheyenne	2005	tree	80.24	19.27
[71]	Street trees	US - Bismack	2005	tree	11.63	20.27
[71]	Street trees	US - Berkley	2005	tree	183.73	72.56
[71]	Street trees	US - Glendal	2005	tree	122.1	13.84
[71]	Street trees	US - California	2006	tree	168.66	
[71]	Street trees	US - California	2006	tree	618	
[72]	Street trees	US - California	2003	tree	7.34	35.10
[73]	Street trees	US - California	2017	tree		17.41
[64]	Trees	Austria	2017	m ²		0.80
[64]	Vegetation	Austria	2017	m ²		3.99
[74]	Street trees	Lisbon	2011	tree		43.51
[75]	Street forest	Review	2018	tree		22.44
[76]	Street trees	China	2018	tree		18.19
[76]	Street trees	China	2018	tree		30.80
[36]	Street trees	EU	2018	tree	90.5	
[36]	Street trees	EU	2018	tree	299.7	
[36]	Street trees	EU	2018	tree	203	
[36]	Street trees	EU	2018	tree	499.5	
[55]	Trees in green space	Brazil	2017	m ²	0.58	0.90
[47]	Urban forestry	US	2011	tree	50.48	15.15
[47]	Urban forestry	US	2011	tree	504.84	65.62
[31]	Trees (green space)	Denmark	2021	tree	1075.85	53.79
[31]	trees (non-paved)	Denmark	2021	tree	5379.24	
[31]	Trees (paved)	Denmark	2021	tree	13,448.09	

Another factor driving the price differences is the specific context that produced the cost figures. Elements such as labor intensity, labor cost, experience, competencies, and industry maturity all affect the costs of constructing and maintaining nature areas that can serve as NbS.

Despite these caveats, the cost estimates provided in Tables 1-4 are informative. The cost figures can be applied to various NbS projects as part of a scoping exercise that will inform analysts if further assessment of specific projects is relevant.

Using Eq. 1, we have calculated total present unit cost for green space, blue spaces, green roofs, and street trees (see Table 5). We do this in order to compare solution across NbS typology. Table 5 is based on median establishment and maintenance cost from Section 3-6. We apply a discount rate of 3 % and assume the project will run for 50 years. Furthermore, we follow Keating et al. [32] in assuming that green space, blue space, and street trees have a lifetime of more than 50 years. Meanwhile we cut the lifetime of green roofs to 40 years following Manso et al. [69], Carter Keeler [70], and GSA [61] assessments of green roofs endurance. Additionally, the blue space is assumed to cover 1 ha.

Given the functional form of Eq. (1) and the choice of the discount rate, the construction cost is given more weight relative to the ongoing maintenance cost. A lower discount rate or a discount rate that decreases over time would give maintenance costs more weight [26]. It is important to note that the calculated cost does not include land opportunity cost considerations, which could potentially change the cost estimates depending on the specific urban setting. The cost figures presented in Table 5 show that green spaces are the least expensive compared to an extensive green roof or a pond. It is difficult to compare street trees in terms of size to the other types of constructed nature areas, as street tree coverage will vary from the foot to the tree's crown.

Table 5
Total present cost of different Nature-based Solutions (in 2021 prices).

Type	Lifetime	Unit	Total Present Cost
Green space	> 50 years	m ²	56 EUR
Blue space (Pond)	> 50 years	m ³	73 EUR
Green roof (Extensive)	40 years	m ²	201 EUR
Street trees	> 50 years	tree	888 EUR

8. Cost-effectiveness analysis of nature-based solutions

In the following section, we demonstrate how the cost measures provided in the previous sections can be applied to make economic assessments of NbS. We achieve this by adapting the cost-effectiveness analysis to accommodate the multi-benefit characteristics of NbS. We explore this innovation using a hypothetical case of a south European municipality considering a new roof for one of its more prominent public buildings.

Traditional cost-effectiveness analyses relate costs to a single effect for different competing proposals [77]. The action with the lowest cost-effectiveness ratio will, *ceteris paribus*, be the best proposal. However, as NbS provide multiple benefits, the conventional assessment in cost-effectiveness analysis may misrepresent the actual effects of NbS. Instead, we suggest ranking all the benefits and then performing a step-wise cost-effectiveness analysis. This ranking could be based on existing local policy objectives determined by local communities or local politicians. In this way, the benefit side of the NbS will be handled pragmatically, bypassing the resource-demanding work of monetarization and valuing benefits in a cost-benefit analysis.

The step-wise cost-effectiveness approach will also create a more transparent process, allowing decision-makers and the public to better understand the basis for choosing between competing solutions. An additional advantage is that precise quantification of the effect is not a necessity. Given that the step-wise ranked cost-effectiveness analysis compares competing solutions, in case of a knowledge gap, it will be sufficient to provide a general assessment of the solution's effect on a scale ranging from high to low impact. We propose an economic assessment of NbS with the least possible information requirements. Only cost estimates will need to be known with some level of confidence.

8.1. Application of the step-wise ranked cost-effectiveness analysis

Suppose a south European municipality is considering a new roof for one of its more prominent public buildings. The municipal officials are likely primarily concerned with the comfort of the building's users, the construction and maintenance costs of the roof, and potential energy

savings. Decisionmakers in the municipality are furthermore likely to prioritize these project objectives in that specific order. The construction cost will influence the municipality's investment budget, while maintenance costs and energy savings will affect the municipality's budget as ongoing expenses.

For simplicity, the municipality is considering two possible roof types: an extensive green roof and a cool roof with a white reflective coating. Since the municipality is located in south Europe, the primary energy consumption concern is cooling, making a cool roof an obvious choice. The municipal official is most likely concerned with the comfort of the building's users, followed by potential energy savings. Additionally, the municipality may have general policy objectives regarding aesthetic and recreational benefits for its citizens, preservation and enhancement of biodiversity, CO₂ mitigation, air quality improvement, and risk reduction from extreme precipitation events. A council in the municipality could rank the costs and benefits of the two roof types as described in Fig. 1.

Several of the ranked benefits are shared between the roof types, including the comfort of users of the building, energy savings, and CO₂ mitigation, while recreational potential, biodiversity protection, air pollution mitigation, and flood risk reduction are benefits that are exclusively related to green roofs [30].

An extensive green roof will cost around 108 EUR/m² to construct and about 2.3 EUR/m² to maintain, according to Section 5. A cool roof will cost 81.6 EUR/m² to construct and 2.86 EUR/m² to maintain, according to Berto et al. [78]. If we assume a lifetime of 40 years for the green roof and a 20-year lifetime for the cool roof, in addition to a nonconvex discount rate of 3 %. A green roof of 400m² will cost 80,114 Euro over a 40-year period, while a cool roof will cost 77,100 Euro over a 40-year period. The result is sensitive to the assumption of the lifetime, the discount rate, and the maintenance cost. Small changes in the assumption can alter the results. The implications are that it is not possible with a high level of certainty to conclude that the cool roof is the cheaper solution relative to the green roof.

The first priority of the ranking is the comfort of the users of the building, sheltering people from the weather elements. The two roof types are likely to provide a similar level of comfort. Thus, the south European municipality is left with no apparent preferred option. Going one step down the ranking, the municipality has emphasized energy saving (see Fig. 1). Francis & Jensen [79] provide an overview of building energy-saving due to reduced cooling requirements as a result

of green roof refurbishment. They find that there is an energy-saving ranging from 2.3 % up to 90 % based on 21 studies. Most of the green roof studies document energy savings of less than 30 %. In contrast, the energy savings of a cool roof are easier to calculate with much higher precision. Rawat Singh [80] find that cool roofs can reduce energy consumption by 17 % in dry, hot climates. Energy consumption can be reduced even further to 32 % and 35 % in temperate and tropical regions, respectively. The cooling effect of green roofs and cool roofs are nonetheless overlapping. Again, there is no obvious choice.

The municipality council is forced to look further down their ranking, and here the green roof outperforms the cool roof. The green roof is likely to have additional aesthetic and recreational values for people who can see the roof, while the cool roof is just a roof. Similarly, a green roof can possibly enhance or preserve existing biodiversity, which the cool roof does not provide. The green roof can also, to some extent, mitigate air pollution by absorbing air pollutants and reducing pressure on sewerage systems in situations with an excessive amount of rainwater [79]. While these benefits are relatively small, the cool roof does not provide any of these benefits. Finally, the uncertainty surrounding energy consumption related to green roofs will also be reflected in the potential CO₂ reduction that both roof types provide.

In the example of a green roof versus a cool roof, the ranking of benefits relative to costs showed that a green roof is likely the preferable choice. The ranking approach, where each benefit is assessed, provides a pathway where the multi-purpose characteristics of NbS can be accounted for while utilizing the simplicity of the cost-effectiveness approach. The example can serve as inspiration for similar assessments of different NbS. Note that the case was chosen for illustrative purposes, as the costs and benefits were relatively comparable, allowing for a clear demonstration of the stepwise ranking approach. In cases with less compatibility between options, fewer steps would be required to provide a policy recommendation.

9. Discussion

In this paper, we provide an overview of the costs associated with nature areas that can serve as NbS. Specifically, we present cost estimates for green and blue spaces in urban and peri-urban areas, along with cost estimates for street trees, green roofs, and green walls. The identified costs can be viewed as a status report of the current knowledge base regarding these solutions. However, it is important to note

Fig. 1. Illustrative ranking of potential benefits for green roofs and cool roofs; green columns are specific to the green roof, while blue columns represent shared benefits with cool roofs.

that these estimates are unlikely to be fully representative. A structural review approach could potentially capture a more representative expressions of costs. Our findings also highlight the need for a more standardized approach to reporting cost data to ensure greater consistency and comparability across studies. This would improve the reliability of cost estimates and better inform decision-making processes for implementing NbS.

We further discuss how cost-effectiveness analysis can be adapted to account for the multiple potential benefits that NbS provide in urban and peri-urban areas and aligning with the planning policy objectives of local authorities. Our approach addresses the inherent limitation of traditional cost-effectiveness analysis, which is typically focused on a singular outcome, whereas NbS deliver multiple, overlapping effects. By adopting a stepwise ranking of policy objectives within the cost-effectiveness framework, we aim to create a more balanced evaluation method that captures the full range of relevant NbS benefits. This approach provides a level playing field for comparing NbS with other solutions, enabling policymakers to make informed choices with minimal available information, while still reflecting the multifaceted nature of these interventions.

In conclusion, the cost measures and stepwise cost-effectiveness analysis proposed in this paper provide a foundation for assessing the cost-effectiveness of NbS in urban settings. However, it is important to note that the cost-effectiveness of NbS is context-specific and varies depending on the specific issues being addressed. Assuming that NbS are universally cost-effective, as according to the definition of NbS by the European Commission [17], is overly simplistic. Instead, cost-effectiveness should be assessed on a case-by-case basis. Economic evaluations must also take into account the multiple benefits that NbSNbS provide.

Traditional decision-support frameworks, such as cost-benefit analysis, often embed normative choices and assumptions, leading to hidden biases that limit their ability to address transformative change and long-term impacts, as highlighted by Mercure et al. [81]. Similarly, multi-criteria analysis can conceal key decisions within technical parameters, potentially steering outcomes in unintended directions [82,83]. Our stepwise approach addresses these limitations by offering a transparent and straightforward framework in which costs are clearly defined and directly related to specific outcomes. This aligns with Mercure et al.'s [81] call for decision-making tools that make critical assumptions explicit, particularly in the context of complex, dynamic systems such as NbS.

The costs of NbS vary significantly both across different categories and within a single category. These variations arise from several factors, including inconsistencies in the reporting of cost components and the varying contexts in which the solutions are implemented. Such disparities introduce considerable uncertainty. Comprehensive and harmonized data on NbS costs remain limited, underscoring the need for more standardized reporting practices. Despite this, it is important to emphasize that this paper represents one of the first efforts to systematically compile cost estimates, providing a valuable status report on current knowledge.

We recognize the necessity for future research to delve deeper into the detailed analysis of various NbS, particularly to support the design phase of planning process, similar to the work of Aerts [60]. Such investigations enhance our understanding of the costs associated with different elements and processes specific to different types of NbS. However, it is important to note that complexity seldom leads to improved predictive power, and these endeavors are not likely to substantially enhance the accuracy of cost predictions - more likely the reverse is to be expected [84–86]. Consequently, these detailed analyses would not necessarily benefit the scoping part of the planning process which has been the objective of this paper. Future research on costs of NbS should therefore focus on two main areas: firstly, providing even more cost data for different NbS to enhance initial scoping efforts; and secondly, directing efforts towards disentangling cost measures to

improve cost assessments during the design phase of the planning process.

The utilization of space is a critical economic aspect of implementing NbS. Space is undeniably a limiting factor in urban and peri urban areas, and the choice to allocate it to NbS inherently involves economic trade-offs. These considerations remain an essential backdrop to understanding the broader economic implications of NbS. Yet, the opportunity costs associated with the use of land or space have not been adequately explored in current research. Future studies should aim to provide a practical monetary evaluation of these costs. This would allow for a more comprehensive integration of these costs into the overall assessment of the viability of NbS, thereby supporting more informed decision-making in urban planning processes.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Toke Emil Panduro: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.
Doan Nainggolan: Writing – review & editing, Data curation.
Marianne Zandersen: Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data is provided in the manuscript.

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